

Future proofing active data management

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

University of Canberra

February 2023

About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

The University of Canberra (UC) Institutional Underpinnings project tested the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) Active Data Management element. In particular, we zoomed in on the 'Integration for a Seamless User Experience' section. We wanted researchers to be able to seamlessly manage project data through its lifecycle, from planning what data could be collected for a project, how it will be stored and analysed, and its publication, archival or disposal. We identified several gaps in UC's data management systems and processes, so we embarked on an ambitious project to integrate three enterprise systems in the University: PURE (Grants Management), ReDBox (research data management planning) and Infonetica (ethics), and to engage UC researchers with how to use these systems for new research projects.

There were two arms to the project, integrating the systems and educating researchers. To begin the first arm, we collaborated with the team from Elsevier (Pure) and ReDBox to integrate these two tools. We utilised Elsevier's help to develop and link Pure and ReDBox 'fields', so information entered into one tool flows into the appropriate place in the other, via application programming interfaces (APIs). The outcome of this project was that following a successful grant application in Pure, the integration is triggered. The named researcher(s) are sent an email congratulating them on the successful award. The email also lets the researcher know that a ReDBox account for the specific project has been created and provides a link that takes the researcher to that ReDBox page where they can then proceed to filling out their data management plan. Importantly, the ReDBox plan comes pre-filled with project information (from Pure) to save the researcher time, so they can focus their attention on where and how they plan to store their data. For instance, key metadata such as the project title, researcher's details (name, email address, Uni ID, faculty/department details) and funding details of the project are pre-populated within the data management plan. An additional benefit of this part of the project was creating an automatic trigger of a DC Data workspace for new research projects; DC Data is a tool which allows researchers to store and collaborate on data and publish data following research project completion. The whole process has been made to be as seamless as possible.

The ReDBox-Pure arm of the project was forecasted to take six months but took around eight months, being held up by technical challenges. For example, systems would go 'down' and took time to be restored, and there were many bugs to fix at the end of the project which delayed 'going live'. We held fortnightly or weekly meetings with Elsevier and QCIF during the integration process especially when setting up test environments to ensure that the correct information flowed between PURE and ReDBox. In parallel, we set up regular meetings with our Funded Research team to align the integration work with their internal processes as we were aware PURE is utilised differently across institutions. We ran a test pilot project with eight researchers (six PhD students and two academic staff), and these staff members assisted greatly in 'live' testing of the user experience, along with ensuring that the correct flow of metadata had been achieved, such as confirming that they had received the automatic notification

emails with the correct working links (or not). This allowed us to incorporate their feedback in our optimisation phase before going live and this contributed to the ‘User-Focused Design’ section within Active Data Management. The PURE-ReDBox integration went live University wide in May 2022. The Pure-Infonetica(-ReDBox) integration is still underway and is forecasted to be live at the end of 2022.

For the second arm of this project, engaging researchers, we embarked on a faculty ‘roadshow’, presenting at each faculty school or research institute. We aimed to have a 1 hour session: half an hour detailing what is data management planning (DMP), what is expected of UC researchers, and how to use UC’s DMP systems; and half an hour of questions. This session also referenced the newly minted DMP pages on the same topics available on UC’s eResearch web pages. We also sought feedback from a DMP survey, and asked key research staff individually about their user experiences. These training materials lean heavily towards our data management policy, procedure and guidelines that were developed in and approved in 2021.

Resulting Improvements

This project has resulted in the creation of a complete and streamlined research data management process for all researchers at the University of Canberra. This has facilitated the University to meet its requirements to provide researchers the means to create DMPs for their research projects, and this has facilitated the creation of presentations, materials and guidelines for researchers to produce high-quality plans for effective data governance. This will ensure safe and secure data management practices at UC.

This integration has been well received by researchers who have since provided positive feedback and made clear they were glad we embarked on this project to integrate systems. For example, “I found it easy to understand and find it very straightforward to understand how and why we need to engage with data management policies. ... I feel the overview session provided was helpful, easy to understand, and RedBox is easy to navigate.” Researchers have also expressed looking forward to the integration of Pure and Infonetica.

Next Steps

We are now in the next phase of integration (PURE – Infonetica). Meetings immediately commenced between our team, Elsevier and Infonetica. A test environment has been created in Infonetica. We are now mapping out fields that need to be integrated, along with setting up the rules for the different ethics forms within Infonetica. And we are finalising presentations and video walkthroughs for how to use ReDBox for researchers. Following this, we will develop similar presentations and guides for accessing storage services at UC, as well as Computation and Training needs.

Project Outputs

Collection of materials used to establish Research Data Management Planning at the University of Canberra. <https://doi.org/10.17632/bfrr75n8wh.1>

We have internally documented the integration and engagement steps to allow this process to be followed by other interested institutions. This includes how the mapping process was undertaken and also how the integration points were mapped. (E.g. APIs generated.) These are now publicly available following finalisation of the Pure-Infonetica integration and DMP engagement strategy across the university research groups. It includes engagement documents developed as part of this project and technical details such as the integration workflow and API connections. This will be of value especially for institutions who already have ReDBox and Pure, and smaller institutions or those who are still maturing in their Data Managing Planning ventures.

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).